

THE CAPACITATED SINGLE ALLOCATION HUB MAXIMAL COVERING PROBLEM WITH HUB INSTALLATION COSTS

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Abstract: *This study considers a variant of the hub maximal covering problem that assumes single allocation scheme, hub capacities and hub installation costs. The objective of the problem is to find optimal locations for opening hubs and optimal allocations of each non-hub node to one of the installed hubs with sufficient capacity such that the sum of uncovered demands for all origin-destination pairs and the hub installation costs is minimized. In the hub location literature, this problem is denoted as the capacitated single allocation hub maximal covering problem. Two four-index integer linear mathematical formulations of the considered problem are presented, together with reformulations into a two-index and a three-index mixed integer linear program. Each of the four presented mathematical formulations is used within the framework of an exact solver to find solutions for the set of modified Australian Post hub instances. The results obtained are compared in respect to the number of optimal solutions and the quality of the upper bounds obtained by the exact solver, as well as the computational times required when using the considered mathematical formulations.*

Keywords: *Hub maximal covering problem, Hub capacities, Hub installation costs, Mathematical programming, Integer linear programming.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Hub covering problems were introduced in (Campbell, 1994) as extensions of the classical covering location problem. In the classical hub covering problem, it is necessary to choose locations for opening hubs and to allocate non-hub nodes to opened hubs, so that each origin-destination (O-D) pair of nodes is covered (Campbell, 1994). An O-D pair is considered "covered" if the distance of the path established via hub nodes is not greater than the specified maximum service distance. The distance between an O-D pair can also be observed as the transportation cost or travel time along the path between an O-D pair via hub nodes.

From the early work by (Campbell, 1994), many variants of hub covering problems have been proposed in the literature. Generally, hub covering problems developed in two main directions: hub set covering and hub maximal covering problems. The goal of the hub set covering problem is to locate hub nodes such that all demands are covered while the cost of opening hub facilities is minimized. The hub maximal covering problem maximizes the demand covered with a fixed number of hubs to be located. An overview of hub covering problems, mathematical formulations, and solution methods can be found in (Alumur et al., 2021; Contreras and O'Kelly, 2019; Karimi and Bashiri, 2011; Wagner, 2008).

Capacitated variants of hub covering problems impose limits on the volume of flow that can be collected at a hub, routed through it, or transported via inter-hub connections. To the best of our knowledge, such capacity constraints have been considered in only a few studies within the existing literature. In (Mohammadi et al., 2011), the capacitated single allocation hub covering problem was considered and a new imperialist competitive algorithm was proposed as a solution method. The capacitated multi-modal multi-product p -hub covering problem under a queuing approach was studied in (Sedehzadeh et al., 2015) and solved by a multi-objective parallel simulated annealing algorithm. In (Hossein Karimi et al., 2016), the authors proposed the multi-modal single allocation capacitated p -hub covering problem over fully interconnected hub networks and used a tabu-search solution approach. The capacitated hub maximal covering problem with transfer flow and hub establishment costs was presented in (Alizadeh et al., 2016) and solved using two multi-objective evolutionary algorithms. The capacitated multiple allocation hub covering flow problem was first introduced in (Sener and Feyzioğlu, 2021).

In this study, we consider a variant of the capacitated single allocation hub maximal covering problem (CSAHMCP), which involves capacity restrictions on incoming flow collected at hubs and fixed costs of opening

hubs. This study extends our previous research on multiple hub covering problem variants (Janković, Mišković, et al., 2017; Janković and Stanimirović, 2017; Todosijević et al., 2024). The considered CSAHMCP arises from the design of various service networks, such as postal delivery, express delivery, logistics, telecommunications, public transportation, etc. In all these networks, it is assumed that a hub node can receive and process a limited amount of flow, and that there are certain expenses when setting up hubs. The number of hubs to be established is not fixed in advance. Each non-hub node sends and receives the flow via exactly one, previously opened hub (single allocation scheme). When choosing hub locations and allocations of non-hub nodes to hubs, the travel time of transporting flow from an origin to destination node through the resulting network must not exceed a certain constant (coverage radius). Only in that case, the transported flow for an O-D pair is considered to be covered. The objective of the CSAHMCP is to minimize the company's total losses, which include the losses (expressed in monetary units) for uncovered flows and the costs of setting up hubs.

The CSAHMCP under consideration is formulated as four equivalent integer or mixed integer linear programs, which are further used within the framework of the commercial CPLEX solver to solve modified AP instances from the literature. The results obtained by the four CSAHMCP formulations are compared in the sense of the quality of obtained solutions and running times required by CPLEX to return either an optimal or a feasible solution. The presented results are analyzed in terms of the number of established hubs in solutions obtained for AP instances with the same dimension but different fixed costs and capacity types.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the four equivalent mathematical formulations of the CSAHMCP are presented. Section 3 presents the results of computational experiments conducted on modified hub instances from the literature, together with the analysis of the presented results. A summary of the study and suggestions for future research directions are provided in Section 4.

2. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATIONS

Let $G(N, E)$ be a complete undirected graph, where N is a set with n nodes, $E = \{(i, j) : i, j \in N\}$ is set of edges, while $H \subseteq N$ is the set of potential hubs. The travel time from origin node i to destination node j via hubs $k, m \in H$ is calculated as $t_{ij}^{km} = \chi t_{ik} + \alpha t_{km} + \delta t_{mj}$, where t_{ij} is the travel time along the edge $(i, j) \in E$. The parameters χ, δ and α multiply travel times from an origin to a hub, from a hub to a destination, and for the inter-hub connections, respectively, and $\alpha < \chi, \delta$ holds. If the travel time t_{ij}^{km} is not greater than a specific value β , the O-D pair $i - j$ is considered to be covered by hubs k and m . The flow of demand T_{ij} from node $i \in N$ to node $j \in N$ is given, and it is not necessary that $T_{ij} = T_{ji}$ holds. For each potential hub $k \in H$, there is capacity limit $g_k \geq 0$ on the flow collected at hub and fixed costs $F_k \geq 0$ for hub installation. Each non-hub node is assigned to exactly one hub (single allocation scheme), while hubs communicate directly with each other. Due to the triangle inequality imposed on t_{ij} , the flow for each O-D pair is routed via at most two hubs. The goal of CSAHMCP is to choose locations for opening hubs from the set $H \subseteq N$ and to allocate each non-hub node to exactly one opened hub, so as to minimize the sum of the total uncovered flow and the costs of hub installations.

The four-index formulation for CSAHMCP uses a binary parameter a_{ij}^{km} , $i, j \in N, k, m \in H$ that takes the value of 1 if $t_{ij}^{km} \leq \beta$, and 0 otherwise. Binary variable x_{ik} takes the value of 1 if node $i \in N$ is allocated to hub $k \in H$, and 0 otherwise. Note that $x_{kk} = 1$ implies that the node k is hub and is assigned to itself. Binary variable y_{ijkm} is equal to 1 if there is traffic from origin node $i \in N$ to destination node $j \in N$ that is routed via hubs $k \in H$ and $m \in H$, respectively, and 0 otherwise. By using this notation, the CSAHMCP may be formulated as a four-index Integer Linear Program (ILP):

$$\min \sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \in N} \sum_{k \in H} \sum_{m \in H} (1 - a_{ij}^{km}) T_{ij} y_{ijkm} + \sum_{k \in N} F_k x_{kk} \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$x_{ik} \leq x_{kk} \quad \forall i \in N \quad \forall k \in H, \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{k \in H} x_{ik} = 1 \quad \forall i \in N, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \in N} T_{ij} x_{ik} \leq g_k x_{kk} \quad \forall k \in H, \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{k \in H} \sum_{m \in H} y_{ijkm} = 1 \quad \forall i, j \in N, \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{m \in H} y_{ijkm} \leq x_{ik} \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad \forall k \in H, \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{k \in H} y_{ijkm} \leq x_{jm} \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad \forall m \in H, \quad (7)$$

$$x_{ik} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in N \quad \forall k \in H, \quad (8)$$

$$y_{ijkm} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad \forall k, m \in H. \quad (9)$$

The objective (1) is to minimize the sum of uncovered demand for all O-D pairs and the cost of hub installations. Constraints (2) and (3) ensure that each non-hub node is assigned to exactly one established hub. The amount of flow collected in each hub is limited by constraints (4). Constraint (5) provides that the flow for each O-D pair $i - j$ is completely routed through a pair of hubs k and m . In this route, the origin i must be assigned to hub k , while destination j must be allocated to hub m , which is ensured by constraints (6) and (7). Finally, constraints (8) and (9) define binary variables x_{ik} and y_{ijkm} , respectively.

The presented four-index formulation for CSAHMCP can be modified as follows. For every $i, j \in H$ and $k, m \in H$, the sets $N_{ij} = \{(k, m) \in H^2 : t_{ij}^{km} \leq \beta\}$, $N'_{ijk} = \{m \in H : t_{ij}^{km} \leq \beta\}$, and $N''_{ijm} = \{k \in H : t_{ij}^{km} \leq \beta\}$ are defined. Moreover, additional binary variables w_{ij} , $i, j \in N$ are introduced, where each w_{ij} equals 1 if the origin-destination pair $i - j$ is uncovered, and 0 otherwise. The resulting modified four-index ILP formulation for CSAHMCP is as follows:

$$\min \sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \in N} T_{ij} w_{ij} + \sum_{k \in N} F_k x_{kk} \quad (10)$$

subject to (2), (3), (4), (8), and

$$\sum_{(k, m) \in N_{ij}} y_{ijkm} + w_{ij} = 1, \quad \forall i, j \in N, \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{m \in N'_{ijk}} y_{ijkm} \leq x_{ik} \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad \forall k \in H, \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{k \in N''_{ijm}} y_{ijkm} \leq x_{jm} \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad \forall m \in H, \quad (13)$$

$$y_{ijkm} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad \forall (k, m) \in H^2. \quad (14)$$

$$w_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i, j \in N. \quad (15)$$

In an O-D pair $i - j$ is not covered, there is no traffic from origin i to destination node j , which is indicated by constraints (11). Constraints (12) and (13) have the same role as constraints (6) and (7). Variables y_{ijkm} and w_{ij} are of binary type, which is denoted by constraints (14) and (15).

In order to present a two-index formulation of CSAHMCP, we use parameter $\lambda_{ij} = \max\{a_{ij}^{km} : k, m \in H\}$ from (Peker and Kara, 2015). For each covered O-D pair $i - j$, we introduce a non-negative variable Z_{ij} representing the fraction of flow routed from origin i to destination j . By using this newly introduced notation, and the notation from the four-index formulation (1)–(9), the CSAHMCP may be modeled as the following two-index Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP):

$$\min \sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \in N} (1 - Z_{ij}) T_{ij} + \sum_{k \in N} F_k x_{kk} \quad (16)$$

subject to (2), (3), (4), (8), and

$$Z_{ij} \leq \sum_{k \in H} a_{ij}^{km} x_{ik} + \lambda_{ij} (1 - x_{jm}), \quad \forall i, j \in N, m \in H \quad (17)$$

$$Z_{ij} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, j \in N. \quad (18)$$

The objective function (16) carries the same interpretation as (1). Note that the newly introduced variables Z_{ij} are now incorporated in the first sum of the objective function in (16). The new constraints (17) provides that the fraction of flow Z_{ij} for a covered O-D pair $i - j$ corresponds to appropriate values of allocation variables x_{ik} and x_{jm} . Coverage variables Z_{ij} are non-negative, which is indicated by constraints (18).

Finally, we present a three-index CSAHMCP formulation that involves the set $G_{ij}^k = \{m \in H : a_{ij}^{km} = 1\}$ for each O–D pair $i - j$ and each hub k . This set contains all hubs $m \in H$ such that the established path $i \rightarrow k \rightarrow m \rightarrow j$ is covered. We also introduce a set of binary variables w_{ijk} , where $i, j \in N, k \in H$. Each variable w_{ijk} corresponds to the set G_{ij}^k and takes the value of 1 if the origin node i is allocated to the hub k and the destination node j is assigned to a hub from the set G_{ij}^k . By using this new set of variables w_{ijk} , together with the set of variables x_{ik}, x_{kk}, Z_{ij} , and the previously defined parameters, the CSAHMCP is formulated as the following three-index MILP: (16) subject to (2)–(4), (8), (18), and

$$w_{ijk} \leq \sum_{m \in G_{ij}^k} x_{jm}, \quad \forall i, j \in N, k \in H \quad (19)$$

$$w_{ijk} \leq x_{ik}, \quad \forall i, j \in N, k \in H \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{k \in H} w_{ijk} \leq 1, \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad (21)$$

$$Z_{ij} \leq \sum_{k \in H} w_{ijk}, \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad (22)$$

$$w_{ijk} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in N, k \in H \quad (23)$$

Constraints (19)–(20) ensure that the variable w_{ijk} takes the value of 1 only if the node i is assigned to hub k and the node j is assigned to some hub m from the set G_{ij}^k . Constraints (21) guarantee that for each O–D pair $i - j$, there is at most one covering path established, while constraints (22) define Z_{ij} as the fraction of the flow between a covered O–D pair $i - j$. Finally, constraints (23) indicate the binary type of variables w_{ijk} .

3. COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

For our numerical experiments, we employed Australian Post (AP) benchmark instances, which incorporate both node-specific fixed costs and capacity constraints, as introduced by (Ernst and Krishnamoorthy, 1998). Each problem size n was expanded into four scenario types by combining tight (T) and loose (L) values for both fixed costs and capacities, resulting in the following configurations: $nTT, nTL, nLT,$ and nLL . The flow cost parameters were fixed at $\delta = \chi = 1$ and $\alpha = 0.75$. Notably, the AP flow matrix is asymmetric, with $T_{ij} \neq T_{ji}$ and $T_{ii} \neq 0$. In all considered AP instances for CSAHMCP, the values of the binary coverage parameter a_{ij}^{km} were adopted as proposed by (Peker and Kara, 2015):

$$a_{ij}^{km} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } t_{ij}^{km} \leq \beta, \quad \forall i, j \in N, \forall k, m \in H \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In case that the two parts of the objective function (the total uncovered demand and the total cost of setting up hubs) are not well balanced, it may lead to a preference for minimizing one part of the objective function. To resolve this issue, we scaled the input data in the objective function, which results in scaling of the two components of the objective function. More precisely, let $T_{total} = \sum_{i, j \in N} T_{ij}$ be the total flow between all O–D pairs, and $Cost_{total} = \sum_{k \in N} F_k$ the total costs of establishing hubs on each potential hub location. The input data T_{ij} and F_k are scaled as follows: $T_{ij} := 100 \cdot T_{ij} / T_{total}$, for each $i, j \in N$ and $F_k := 100 \cdot F_k / Cost_{total}$, for each $k \in N$. As the original amounts of flow T_{ij} between O–D pairs $i - j$ are now scaled, the given capacities of each potential hub must also be scaled: $g_k := 100 \cdot g_k / T_{total}$, for every $k \in N$. The results of preliminary computational experiments have shown that the scaling of $T_{ij}, F_k,$ and g_k leads to a balance of the impact of the two parts in the objective function. The values of the coverage parameter β are set to the corresponding solution values for the uncapacitated multiple allocation p -hub center problem (UMApHCP) from (Brimberg et al., 2017) with $p = 5$ hubs (for AP instances with $n \leq 50$) and $p = 10$ hubs (for AP instances with $n = 100$).

Table 1 presents the results obtained by the CPLEX solver using each of the four CSAHMCP formulations on the modified AP instances with up to 100 nodes. Note that all computational experiments are performed on an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7820HQ CPU @ 2.90GHz with OS Windows 11 Pro. The first two columns of Table 1 contain instance's name and the value of parameter β . For each mathematical formulation analyzed, the remaining columns of Table 1 provide detailed information. These include the number of hubs that were opened in the solutions found by the CPLEX solver, which is displayed under the column labeled *hubs*. The column titled *value* reports either the optimal solutions identified by CPLEX or, if the solver did not manage to find an optimal solution within the one-hour time limit, the corresponding upper bounds are shown and marked with

Table 1: Computational results on AP instances with up to 100 nodes

Inst.	β	four-index form.			modified four-index form.			three-index form.			two-index form.						
		hubs	value	gap	time	hubs	value	gap	time	hubs	value	gap	time				
10TT	30371.32	4	39.43	0.00	1.09	4	39.43	0.00	0.34	4	39.43	0.00	0.20	4	39.43	0.00	0.20
10TL	30371.32	2	46.07	0.00	1.14	2	46.07	0.00	0.37	2	46.07	0.00	0.16	2	46.07	0.00	0.20
10LL	30371.32	2	38.16	0.00	2.23	2	38.16	0.00	0.63	2	38.16	0.00	0.17	2	38.16	0.00	0.17
10LT	30371.32	2	34.44	0.00	2.08	2	34.44	0.00	0.42	2	34.44	0.00	0.17	2	34.44	0.00	0.18
20TT	37868.15	3	15.29	0.00	148.48	3	15.29	0.00	52.44	3	15.29	0.00	3.75	3	15.29	0.00	2.90
20TL	37868.15	3	18.81	0.00	224.72	3	18.81	0.00	45.67	3	18.81	0.00	5.99	3	18.81	0.00	7.20
20LL	37868.15	1	13.03	0.00	240.22	1	13.03	0.00	38.25	1	13.03	0.00	2.13	1	13.03	0.00	1.76
20LT	37868.15	1	11.51	0.00	242.66	1	11.51	0.00	42.07	1	11.51	0.00	3.74	1	11.51	0.00	1.86
25TT	45552.50	3	9.07	0.00	682.15	3	9.07	0.00	317.82	3	9.07	0.00	47.01	3	9.07	0.00	8.66
25TL	45552.50	3	12.06	0.00	908.21	3	12.06	0.00	271.39	3	12.06	0.00	41.79	3	12.06	0.00	13.86
25LL	45552.50	1	9.54	0.00	1488.10	1	9.54	0.00	589.96	1	9.54	0.00	44.20	1	9.54	0.00	26.24
25LT	45552.50	2	7.77	0.00	1615.01	2	7.77	0.00	587.43	2	7.77	0.00	58.68	2	7.77	0.00	15.48
40TT	49741.20	14	60.56*	>100.00	3600.00	-	-	-	-	5	6.10	0.00	1058.93	5	6.10	0.00	748.03
40TL	49741.20	14	61.73*	>100.00	3600.00	-	-	-	-	3	8.82*	0.00	3600.00	3	8.82	0.00	855.22
40LL	49741.20	3	56.21*	>100.00	3600.00	3	56.21*	>100.00	3600.00	2	5.89	0.00	929.79	2	5.89	0.00	242.27
40LT	49741.20	3	56.80*	>100.00	3600.00	3	56.80*	>100.00	3600.00	2	3.98	0.00	669.75	2	3.98	0.00	192.40
50TT	50707.87	-	-	-	-	5	93.37*	>100.00	3600.00	-	-	-	-	4	5.44	0.00	1472.04
50TL	50707.87	-	-	-	-	5	83.10*	>100.00	3600.00	-	-	-	-	3	7.46	0.00	2235.23
50LL	50707.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	4.70	0.00	1211.02
50LT	50707.87	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	3.42	0.00	1430.38
100TT	51860.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
100TL	51860.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
100LL	51860.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
100LT	51860.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

an asterisk (*). The best or optimal values are highlighted in bold. In instances where CPLEX was unable to produce any feasible solution due to memory or time restrictions, a dash ("-") is used. Furthermore, the table presents the optimality gap expressed as a percentage, indicating the difference between the best known solution and the bound returned by CPLEX. Finally, the CPU time in seconds is reported, indicating how long CPLEX took to find an optimal solution or to confirm the lower and upper bounds.

Table 1 demonstrates that the CPLEX solver, utilizing the two-index formulation, efficiently found optimal solutions for all AP instances with up to 50 nodes, with an average computation time of 423.27 seconds. However, it failed to identify any feasible solutions for instances with 100 nodes within the one-hour time limit. When employing the three-index formulation, CPLEX was unable to solve one instance (40TL) among the sixteen tested with up to 40 nodes. Furthermore, for instances with 50 and 100 nodes, the solver exhausted memory resources before generating feasible solutions. The four-index formulations exhibited the poorest performance, with no optimal solutions for instances exceeding 25 nodes. While the first four-index approach yielded feasible solutions for 40-node instances, it failed on larger problems. The modified four-index formulation produced feasible solutions for select instances (40LL, 40LT, 50TT, 50TL), yet was unsuccessful for others, including 40TT and 40TL. Analysis of the reported CPU times confirms that the two-index formulation outperforms the three-index and both four-index formulations in computational efficiency.

A comparative analysis of AP instance groups that share the same number of nodes but differ in the combination of fixed costs and capacity settings (n_{TT} , n_{TL} , n_{LL} , and n_{LT}) reveals consistent trends in the obtained solutions. Instances characterized by both tight fixed costs and tight capacities (TT) tend to produce solutions with the highest number of opened hubs. This outcome is expected, as nodes with high flow volumes, otherwise suitable for hub locations, are discouraged by restrictive costs and limited capacity, leading the model to distribute hub openings more broadly. In TL-type instances, where capacities are relaxed but fixed costs remain tight, the number of hubs generally decreases. However, this simplification results in a higher objective function value compared to TT cases. A comparable effect is observed in LT-type instances, where fixed costs are reduced but tight capacities are maintained. Overall, instances of type LL, characterized by both relaxed fixed costs and capacities, tend to yield the fewest established hubs, but also exhibit the highest values of the objective function. This tendency intensifies as the number of nodes increases.

4. CONCLUSION

This study presents four mathematical formulations for the capacitated single allocation maximal covering location problem (CSAHMCP), including two four-index integer linear programming formulations, one two-index, and one three-index mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) formulation. The problem is classified as NP-hard, given that it generalizes its uncapacitated counterpart, which has already been proven to be NP-hard.

The experimental analysis was carried out on a set of Australian Post (AP) benchmark instances containing up to 100 nodes, each defined by specific capacity limits and installation costs for potential hub locations. Among the formulations examined, the two-index MILP formulation contains the smallest number of variables and constraints. As expected, the computational results confirmed that the two-index formulation outperforms the other three in both solution quality and average CPLEX runtime. In the case of 100-node instances, all four CSAHMCP formulations failed to produce a feasible solution within the imposed computational limits using the CPLEX solver. Future work will focus on considering different allocation strategies and incorporating the concept of partial coverage into the hub covering formulation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research conducted in this paper was partially supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia through the institutional grants for the year 2025 to University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mathematics, and University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Economics.

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